

Making large object displays accessible to all

The experiences of Imperial War Museum Duxford

Carl Warner

Large-object accessibility

- Not just a legal requirement - a social responsibility
- Inherent tension:
- Blind and partially sighted people often engage using touch.
- Exhibits do not often respond well to touch!
- What CAN we do?

Some quotes

- ‘I wouldn’t tackle a site this like this on my own – but it’s very frustrating if all the choices are made for me when I get there’
- ‘If all I can do is walk past things that are notionally there I might as well stay at home’
- ‘Don’t assume I can’t see anything at all - most people still have some useful sight’
- ‘I don’t want to be still ploughing through sheets of Braille while my family are enjoying ice cream in the cafe’
- **PLEASE DO NOT TOUCH THE EXHIBITS**

What's wrong with touching?

What can a visitor learn just by touching?

AirSpace

- The story of British and Commonwealth aviation
- Interpret achievements of the past, educate and inspire the pilots and engineers of tomorrow
- Exhibitions Gallery and Aircraft Hall
- Clore Learning Centre and Corporate spaces
- £26 million project, supported by Heritage Lottery Fund and BAE Systems
- Exhibitions budget £3 million

Exhibitions Gallery

Aircraft Hall

Approach

- Direct communication with people with disabilities
- Written guidance from organisations representing people with disabilities
- Advice from Museum colleagues
- If you consult, people are helpful, and understand your problems
- Whatever your budget, something can always be improved.

A package for all

- Pre-visit information
- Map for All
- Accessible graphics
- Develop and integrate things that CAN be touched
- All films subtitled/BSL
- Alternatives – oral history/transcripts
- Braille/raised lettering
- Audio guide
- Train volunteers/staff in audio description?

- That's before we get to the exhibits...

Pre-visit info

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IMPERIAL WAR MUSEUM DUXFORD

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Accessibility

 All our front-of-house staff receive training in disability awareness. If you have queries, or need assistance please ask. They will be more than happy to help you.

The majority of Duxford's buildings have level entry or ramped access for wheelchair users. There are nineteen disabled parking bays and a dropping-off zone for coaches.

Manual folding wheelchairs and three mobility scooters are available for hire. There is no charge, but identification will be required. To reserve, please call our Visitor Centre on 01223 499 314.

Free on-site transport is available throughout the day for visitors who require assistance around the site. A wheelchair can be accommodated to the rear of the vehicle and folded wheelchairs can also be placed at the front of the vehicle. Please note that for safety reasons this service does not run on air show days or busy event days.

Wheelchair accessible toilet facilities available throughout the site.

On days when no special events or attractions are operating, visitors with restricted mobility may be permitted to drive around the site in their own vehicle - please ask the admissions staff.

 Assistance dogs are welcome.

Hands-on educational sessions for students with disabilities are available from the Department for Learning on request. The department also offers talks for students with learning difficulties and a two-day special needs events on the subject of flight. Contact Duxford's Department for Learning on 01223 499 341 for further details.

Search

 [Pre-visit information for visitors with disabilities \(to Duxford\)](#) (31 Kb)

Map for all

Make graphics accessible

Undercarriage

A major cause of **drag** is the undercarriage.

An aeroplane needs an undercarriage so it can move around on the ground.

Many aeroplanes have undercarriages that fold away.

Passenger and military aeroplanes have undercarriages that fold away (retract) as soon as the aeroplane leaves the ground. This reduces **drag** when the aeroplane is in the air.

An Airbus A330, with undercarriage down.

Want to know more?

Retractable undercarriages became popular in the 1930s. Before this time, nearly all aeroplanes had fixed undercarriages that did not fold away.

Today, many small aeroplanes still have fixed undercarriages, which do not fold away. This increases **drag**, but keeps the aeroplane lightweight, because a raising and lowering mechanism can be very heavy.

Some of these fixed undercarriages can have streamlined metal covers, called fairings. These smooth the shape of the undercarriage so it can pass through the air more easily.

Go to the balcony and look at the REB. Can you see its fixed undercarriage?

When you are downstairs look at Concorde. Where do its wheels go after it takes off?

BSL/Subtitling

Create tactile opportunities

Tactile options

Using materials to build aircraft

What is fabric?

Often used as the skin on aircraft, fabric makes an aeroplane streamlined and aerodynamic because it is light and flexible.

Woods of natural grain are used because they are strong and can be worked and finished. They are treated to become hard and strong and can be made into the shapes needed for the aircraft.

Working and joining materials

Different materials are worked and joined together in different ways. We call these construction techniques.

Working with wood

Wooden components are built up in a series of layers. These are joined together with glue and other materials and covered in fabric or metal. The whole structure is then treated to make it strong.

Each piece of wood is worked to create a smooth surface. The wooden skins, spars and ribs are then joined together with glue and other materials to make the structure. The pieces of wood are held together in place while the glue dries and the structure is finished.

Working with fabric

The fabric is stretched over the structure and held in place by the ribs and spars. The fabric is then treated to make it strong and resistant to the elements. The fabric is then joined to the structure with glue and other materials.

Wooden propellers

A propeller is made of different types of wood and is joined together with glue and other materials. The propeller is then treated to make it strong and resistant to the elements.

Plywood

Plywood is made of many thin layers of wood glued together. Plywood uses the natural properties of wood in the best way.

Plywood uses the fact that wood is strong across the grain. The layers are glued together with the grain running in different directions. This makes the plywood strong in any direction.

Plywood can be used instead of solid wood to give extra strength in particular areas, such as around the cockpit. Some aircraft are made of plywood or other types of wood, as was the case with the Douglas Dakota built in the 1930s.

This is a piece of plywood. It is made from several layers of wood.

Wood in the right way

Wood is strong or weak depending on how you use it.

Individual fibres that run through the grain of the wood are the strongest. The wood is strong when the force is applied along the grain. The wood is weak when the force is applied across the grain. The wood is strongest when the force is applied along the grain and the wood is weakest when the force is applied across the grain.

Try bending this piece of wood.

There are still a lot of things that can be made from wood. It is a very versatile material.

The aircraft structure

The aircraft structure is made of metal and wood. The metal is used for the main structure and the wood is used for the skin and other parts. The structure is then treated to make it strong and resistant to the elements.

What are metals?

Metals are strong and hard. They are used for the main structure of the aircraft. Metals are also used for the skin and other parts. Metals are treated to make them strong and resistant to the elements.

Types of metal

There are many different types of metal. Some are stronger than others. Some are lighter than others. Some are more resistant to corrosion than others. The type of metal used depends on the part of the aircraft.

Tactile options

Can I touch?

You can touch these pieces of wood and fabric, but we ask you not to touch the real aircraft and exhibits here at Duxford. Wood and fabric aircraft can be very fragile, and can be damaged very easily by handling. Help us preserve the aircraft by not touching them.

Models and touch

Touchscreen accessibility?

Tactile opportunities

Back to the large objects

Audio guide

Touch this!

If you can't touch, build word pictures

A staff-led touch tour?

Main message – consult!

